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APPLICATION OF REVERSE EMULSIONS FOR SILENCING AND STIMULATION OF OIL WELLS AT THE UZEN FIELD

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Abstract

Over the past decades, the strategic direction in solving these problems has been the development of methods for influencing the formation as a whole, which are currently quite well developed and widely used in the fields. After major or current repairs, there is a decrease in productivity in all wells as a result of the contamination of the productive reservoir during jamming and actual repair. One of the main reasons for the decrease in the productivity of wells after repair is the inconsistency of the applied jamming fluids (JF) with geological and technical conditions.

The task of the well jamming operation is to ensure safe working conditions for drilling and repair crews in the wellbore by preventing the release of oil or gas from the reservoir. The use of reverse emulsions for silencing and stimulation of oil wells stimulates. The goal is to improve the composition of reverse emulsions for silencing and stimulation of oil wells.

The solution of this problem is possible with the help of various compositions of silencing formations that create pressure at the bottom of wells above the reservoir. By changing the composition of the jamming fluid, it is possible to obtain a reverse emulsion designed for jamming wells and simultaneous processing of the bottom-hole zone of the productive formation.

Keywords: *deposit, silencing, emulsion, bottom-hole zone of a productive formation.*

The Uzen field is an oil and gas field in the Mangystau region of Kazakhstan, on the Mangyshlak peninsula. It belongs to the South Mangystau oil and gas region.

It was discovered in 1961 by driller Gaziz Abdrazakov. Deposits at a depth of 0.9-2.4 km. The oil flow rate is 10-81 t/day. Gas flow rate from 8,0 to 230 thousand m³/day. Oil density is 844-874 kg/m³, sulfur content is 0.16-2%, paraffins are 16-22%, resins are 8-20%.

Oil reserves are 1.1 billion tons. The mining center is the city of Zhanaozen.

The operator of the field is the Kazakh oil company KazMunayGas Exploration Production. Oil production in 2008 amounted to 7 million tons. The record level of oil production — 16.3 million tons — was recorded in 1975, the minimum — 2.7 million tons — in 1994.

The reverse emulsions applied at the field during well silencing and simultaneous processing of the bottom-hole zone of the productive formation, consists of an external [1-6] (dispersion) medium, an internal (dispersed) phase and an emulsifier-stabilizer. A distinctive feature of this emulsion is that the composition of the dispersion medium contains a hydrocarbon solvent.

The components of the reverse emulsion are taken in the following ratio. volume %: oil (commercial) - 30-10; hydrocarbon solvent - 29.0-27.5; emulsifier - 1.0-2.5; aqueous phase-40-60

If necessary, a solid weighting agent (barite, siderite, hematite) up to 25% by volume can be

introduced into the composition of the finished emulsion.

Oil should be anhydrous and preferably low-viscosity.

As a hydrocarbon solvent, a wide fraction of light hydrocarbons is used, which is obtained during the preparation of oil at the COTS (complex oil treatment site) and is called "Distillate" in field practice. Before entering into the emulsion, the distillate must be degassed.

ES-2, a reagent used to stabilize hydrophobic emulsion solutions, is used as an emulsifier.

Reservoir water containing calcium ions, aqueous solutions of CaCl₂, NaCl, MgCl₂ salts of any concentration, as well as their mixtures can be used as an aqueous phase.

A solid weighting agent (barite, siderite, hematite, etc.) is introduced when high values of the density of the reverse emulsion are required. The weighting agent is used only conditioned, i.e. dry and loose.

The reverse emulsion has the best technological parameters with an aqueous phase content of 40-50% and a hydrocarbon solvent content in the external environment of at least 50%. These parameters can be within the following limits: density, kg/ m³ - 900-1400; conditional viscosity, c - 50-200; static shear stress, mgs / cm² after 1 min and 10 min - 6-15 and 8-25; filtration index, cm³ / 30 min - at least 3, including for hydrocarbon medium, % - not less than 80; electrical stability, (volts) B - 80-200; solvent capacity - at the level of pure distillate.

Reverse emulsions of the above composition, which have a solvent ability to paraffin and asphalt-resinous deposits, can be used in wells with bottom-hole temperatures up to 80 ° C, and weighted with a solid

weighting agent - in wells with bottom-hole temperatures up to 50 ° C (Figure 1).

The solidification temperature of reverse emulsions is determined by the solidification temperature of the hydrocarbon medium.

Figure 1. Reverse emulsion of the ES-2 brand

Usually, aqueous formulations with additives of thickeners or mineral salts are used for these purposes. It is also possible to use special mechanical reservoir cut-offs or anti-blowout equipment.

When preparing a well for a secondary opening, processing of the bottomhole zone or repair work, the entire trunk is filled with jamming fluid.

The technology of fluid replacement in the borehole consists in carrying out the operation of flushing the borehole with the admission of tubing to the bottom or sequentially replacing the borehole fluid in the well-head-pump section with a silencing fluid to ensure filling of the entire borehole [6-8]. One of the main parameters of the jamming fluid is its density.

The density of the silencing fluid determines the amount of pressure at the bottom of the wells. The main goals and objectives of silencing operations of productive formations:

- The silencing fluid must ensure that the pressure at the bottom exceeds the reservoir pressure.
- The silencing fluid must be chemically inert to the rocks composing the reservoir, compatible with reservoir fluids and must exclude irreversible colmation of the pores of the formation by solid particles. The content of suspended particles should not exceed 30 mg/l.
- The silencing liquid filtrate should have an inhibitory effect on clay particles, preventing their swelling at any pH value of reservoir water.
- The silencing fluid should not form water barriers and should contribute to the hydrophobization of the collector surface and the reduction of capillary pressures in the formation pores by reducing the interfacial tension at the interface of the phases "silencing fluid - reservoir fluid" [7-10].
- The silencing liquid should not form persistent oil-water emulsions of the 1st and 2nd kind.
- The rheological properties of the silencing fluid should be regulated in order to prevent its absorption by the productive reservoir.
- The silencing fluid must have a low corrosive effect on Downhole equipment. The corrosion rate of steel should not exceed 0.12 mm/year
- The silencing fluid must be thermostable at high temperatures and be frost-resistant in winter conditions.
- The silencing fluid must be non-flammable, explosion-proof, non-toxic.

At the same time, technologies for the preparation of jamming fluid and their application in wells should ensure ease of preparation and regulation of the properties of the jamming fluid without creating emergency situations and complications in wells.

Well jamming technologies should not hinder the subsequent development and output of wells to the planned operating mode. Factors that worsen the properties of the CCD when jamming fluids penetrate into it:

- swelling of clay minerals contained in reservoir rock;
- blocking effect of water caused by capillary and surface phenomena occurring in the pore space as a result of mutual displacement of immiscible liquids;
- formation of resistant oil-water emulsions in the formation;
- formation of insoluble sediments in the pore space as a result of the interaction of the silencing fluid and reservoir fluids;
- clogging of pores with solid particles penetrating into the formation together with the filtrate (liquid phase).

All silencing fluids are conditionally divided into 2 groups:

- - water-based, in pm foams, fresh and reservoir waters; solutions of mineral salts; clay solutions; hydrogels; direct emulsions.
- - hydrocarbon-based, in pm commercial or thickened oil; reverse emulsions with an aqueous phase content of up to 70%.

In the group of water-based silencing fluids, the leading role belongs to aqueous solutions of mineral salts or pure brines that do not contain a solid phase.

Complicating factors in silencing wells with mineral salts:

- Interaction of water and salt solutions with clay minerals
- Formation of poorly soluble salts
- Formation of emulsions
- Formation of a water blockade

Additives to aqueous silencing solutions that reduce the negative impact of aqueous solutions of silencing fluids on the formation filtration and capacitance properties (FCP):

Salt deposition inhibitors;

Corrosion inhibitors;
Hydrophobizers and inhibitors of clay swelling;
Demulsifiers.
Salt deposition inhibitors

To prevent the penetration of salt-based silencing fluids into the formation, various thickened silencing fluids are used, which have increased viscosity and have a low filtration coefficient into the formation. The use of thickened silencing fluids is associated with reduced reservoir pressure when the reservoir pressure is lower than hydrostatic.

Thickened silencing fluids on a hydrocarbon basis. For maximum preservation of reservoir properties of productive formations during the repair work in wells, hydrocarbon-based solutions are recommended as a silencing fluid. The use of such systems preserves the natural water saturation of the pores.

The swelling of clay minerals of the formation is excluded; the blocking effect of water caused by capillary phenomena; the formation of insoluble sediments in contact with mineralized waters; corrosion of equipment, hydrogen sulfide manifestations at the wellhead. The disadvantage of hydrocarbon-based silencing fluids is their fire safety.

Thickened hydrocarbon-based liquids can be divided into reverse emulsions and thickened oil.

Due to the breadth of the range of regulated properties and the relatively low cost, reverse emulsions have found the most widespread.

Reverse emulsions for silencing wells. Currently, emulsion compositions are widely used in various oil production processes: in the processes of primary and secondary opening of productive formations, during well silencing, during treatment of the bottom-hole zone of the formation and in the processes of enhanced oil recovery. At the same time, in each specific case, certain types of emulsions and emulsion compositions specially selected taking into account the necessary physical and chemical properties are used.

Thickened oil. The use of thickened oil makes it possible to reduce the negative effect of the jamming fluid on the PZP and obtain a jamming fluid density of less than 1 g / cm³. However, with these advantages, thickened oil has a number of significant disadvantages, in pm, the high cost of the extinguishing fluid; high fire safety; complex regulation of rheological properties.

Well jamming technology. To determine the jamming technology, it is necessary to make a number of decisions:

- composition of the main silencing fluid and additives;
- the need to use a blocking fluid.
- The number of jamming cycles is determined by the depth of the downhole equipment.

By default, the process of pumping the jamming fluid should be carried out into the pipe space of the well (direct method). When it is not possible to knock down the pump valve, jamming is performed through the annulus (reverse method).

In the case of high reservoir pressure, when the pressure significantly exceeds the hydrostatic, the in-

jection rate should be maximum, exceeding the productivity of the well, provided that the pressure does not exceed the maximum permissible (according to the pressure conditions of the crimping column or cable entry).

In the case of normal and low reservoir pressure, the pressure is approximately equal to or lower than the hydrostatic pressure in order to minimize downhole pressure, reduce the volume of absorption of borehole fluid by the reservoir, the injection rate of the silencing fluid should not exceed 10 m³/hour.

Conclusions. Before drawing up a work plan, it is necessary to determine how the first batch of jamming fluid will arrive at the bottom of the wells. The first pack usually includes a blocking compound.

For Uzen deposits with low permeability of the productive layer or high clay content of the rock, a deposition method is recommended. To determine the required volume of the silencing fluid, it is necessary to calculate the internal volume of the well, taking into account the wall thickness of the pipes, the volume of the lowered tubing, and the depth of the descent of the GNO.

The volume of the first jamming cycle is calculated from the condition that it must be at least the internal volume of the production column in the interval from the depth of the descent of the GNP (tubing shoe) before artificial slaughter.

The volume of the second cycle is calculated from the condition that it must be at least the internal volume of the production column minus the volume of tubing in the interval from the mouth to the depth of the descent of the GNO (tubing shoe). I.e., it must provide a complete change of fluid during flushing in the specified volume.

Possible complications in silencing wells:

- Initially incorrect choice of silencing fluid density
- Overflow of the well as a result of an increase in downhole pressure
- In wells with low-permeability reservoirs, it was found that the recovery period of reservoir pressure lasts from 15 to 20 days, and for a number of wells this period reaches 30 days.

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